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№ 1

Muhandislik va Iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy,
innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid
ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
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- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
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- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari

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USING DATA MINING TECHNOLOGIES TO OPTIMIZE QUERIES IN AN UNSTRUCTURED DATA WAREHOUSE

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Abstract: This article discusses the problems of personal identification of individuals whose data partially or completely do not match when transferring data from one server to another in automated information systems. This article presents an optimal identification algorithm in the form of a Data Mining process that allows searching for individuals and legal entities in the database based on fuzzy comparisons. This allows for quick data extraction from users information systems. The algorithm is implemented in the Oracle 18g DBMS in the PL-SQL language.

Key words: interdepartmental data exchange, identification, fuzzy comparison, search for individual details, intelligent comparison function, personal identification number.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada avtomatlashtirilgan axborot tizimlarida ma'lumotlarni bir serverdan ikkinchi serverga o'tkazishda ma'lumotlari qisman yoki to'liq mos kelmaydigan shaxslarni shaxsiy identifikatsiyalash muammolari muhokama qilinadi. Ushbu maqolada ma'lumotlar bazasida jismoniy va yuridik shaxslarni loyqa taqqoslashlar asosida qidirish imkonini beruvchi Ma'lumotlarni qazib olish jarayoni ko'rinishidagi optimal identifikatsiya algoritmi keltirilgan. Bu foydalanuvchilarning axborot tizimlaridan tezkor ma'lumotlarni olish imkonini beradi. Algoritm Oracle 18g DBMS da PL-SQL tilida amalga oshiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: idoralararo ma'lumotlar almashinuvi, identifikatsiya, noaniq taqqoslash, individual tafsilotlarni qidirish, aqlli taqqoslash funktsiyasi, shaxsiy identifikatsiya raqami.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются проблемы персональной идентификации лиц, данные которых частично или полностью не совпадают при передаче данных с одного сервера на другой в автоматизированных информационных системах. В статье представлен оптимальный алгоритм идентификации в виде процесса Data Mining, позволяющий осуществлять поиск физических и юридических лиц в базе данных на основе нечетких сравнений. Это позволяет быстро извлекать данные из информационных систем пользователей. Алгоритм реализован в СУБД Oracle 18g на языке PL-SQL.

Ключевые слова: межведомственный обмен данными, идентификация, нечеткое сравнение, поиск индивидуальных реквизитов, интеллектуальная функция сравнения, персональный идентификационный номер.

INTRODUCTION

For optimal management of large amounts of data related to the details of individuals, it is necessary to provide centralized regulations for storing such characteristics as full name, date of birth, address, passport data, etc. Recently, various departments – holders of local databases (DB) are trying to combine arrays to simplify and improve the quality of work. An intelligent algorithm for searching for individuals in a DB, or identification of details of individuals, comes to the rescue.

For ease of data processing, each set of details in the DB is assigned a so-called personal identification number (PIN). In the case of processing or transferring data about an individual, all binding is carried out specifically to this PIN. In Uzbekistan, unfortunately, there is no single database with the details of all residents, so different departments maintain their own separate register of individuals and create their own PINs. The problem arises when exchanging information about residents between organizations, since it is necessary to link incoming details to existing ones[8]. For unambiguous linking, it is necessary to conduct an intelligent search for an individual in the receiving database, which should take into account many factors: potential errors in manual entry, and missing or outdated details, etc. It is natural to assume that it is advisable to implement such a search in the form of specialized software.

Data Mining is a multidisciplinary field that arose and is developing on the basis of such sciences as applied statistics, pattern recognition, artificial intelligence, database theory, etc. This technology is well suited for implementing the solution to the described problem of interdepartmental information exchange, since it allows you to form an algorithm with a built-in decision-making system to improve the quality of identifying details of individuals. The tools of this technology also allow for intelligent comparison of two data sets and identification of patterns in similar data to improve the quality of search based on fuzzy comparison.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

In the works of J. Usmanov, big data, their analytical analysis, decision-making methods, and integration of information systems were discussed in detail. In addition, foreign customs information systems and their optimization mechanisms were discussed in detail[3].

In the scientific research of A. Saidov, we can see many scientific studies on systematic analysis, information processing, optimal information exchange between information systems, decision-making, theory and practice of intellectual analysis[1].

D. Osipov, on the other hand, touched upon many issues such as intellectual decision-making, big data and analytics, decision-making, information search and extraction, and optimal management[2].

S. Bolotova, on the other hand, touched upon the methods of subjective intelligence, its application in the economic and social spheres, and the issue of decision support. In general, research was carried out aimed at intellectual processing of information[10].

Identification of individuals in a database is designed to solve one of the most important problems in interdepartmental information exchange that arises due to the lack of a single PIN — the lack of an unambiguous correspondence between an individual and a set of his or her basic details (full name, date of birth, address, etc.).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research topic of using data mining technologies to optimize queries in unstructured data warehouses used mathematical and statistical analysis, comparison, systematic analysis and decision-making, and intellectual analysis methods.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Designing an identification algorithm taking into account the Data Mining technology made it possible to create a self-learning procedure that operates automatically.

The paper proposes a search algorithm that includes the following stages: free search (including validation) predictive modeling exception analysis.

Free search (Discovery). At this stage, the original data set is studied in order to find hidden patterns. Preliminary hypotheses regarding the type of patterns are not determined here.

In relation to the identification procedure under consideration, this stage is implemented as an extended search for a request that returns data remotely similar to the set of details of the individual being sought. It is at this stage that patterns are sought that allow the found rule to be applied during subsequent identifications, which speeds up the entire process tens of time (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the process of intelligent data analysis (on the example of tax authorities).

Predictive Modeling. The second stage uses the results of the first stage. Here, the discovered patterns are used directly for forecasting.

At this stage, the developed identification algorithm accumulates the so-called “experience of past identifications” and records it in a specially designated place for use next time. At the third stage, exceptions or anomalies identified in the discovered patterns are analyzed. The action performed at this stage is deviation detection. To identify deviations, it is necessary to determine the norm, which is calculated at the free search stage.

At the third stage, the identification procedure removes from the set of discovered patterns all data obtained by mistake. For example, incorrectness and absence of some details of an individual may lead to the identification of an erroneous pattern, which in turn, if used, will give incorrect conclusions about the identification of such data sets. Therefore, in the proposed algorithm, the final stage is the third stage - the analysis of exceptions.

Knowledge management. The information component plays a vital role in effective business management, so the ability of enterprises to provide their employees with everything necessary to make informed decisions is of great importance. Since the mid-90s of the 20th century, companies have been rapidly interested in software products that allow analysts to work with large volumes of data accumulated in ERP, CRM systems and data warehouses and extract useful information from them. The result was the emergence of new information technologies and tools that provide secure access to corporate data sources and have advanced capabilities for consolidation, analysis, data presentation and distribution of ready-made analytical documents within the organization and beyond: data marts, ad-hoc query processing, reporting, OLAP tools (On-Line Analytical Processing), intelligent data analysis (DM - Data Mining), knowledge discovery in databases (KDD - Knowledge Discovery in Databases), etc. "Data analysis" is understood as actions aimed at extracting information from them about the object under study and obtaining new data based on the available data. Intelligent data analysis (IDA) is a general term for data analysis with the active use of mathematical methods and algorithms (optimization methods, genetic algorithms, pattern recognition, statistical methods, data mining, etc.) using visual representation of data. The general scheme of intelligent analysis is shown in Fig. 1.

- 1) identifying patterns (free search);
- 2) using identified patterns to predict unknown values (forecasting);
- 3) exception analysis to identify and interpret anomalies in the found patterns.

Sometimes an intermediate stage of checking the reliability of the found patterns (validation stage) is distinguished between their discovery and use.

All IDA methods are divided into two groups according to the principle of working with the initial data:

1. Methods of reasoning based on case analysis - the initial data can be stored in an explicit detailed form and directly used for forecasting and/or analysis. The disadvantage of this group of methods is the complexity of their use on large volumes of data.

2. Methods for identifying and using formalized patterns that require extracting information from primary data and transforming it into some formal constructions, the type of which depends on the specific method. Fig. 2 shows the methods included in these groups.

The consolidation procedure is based on the ETL (extraction, transformation, loading) process. The ETL process solves the problems of extracting data from different types of sources, transforming them into a form suitable for storage in a certain structure, and loading them into the appropriate database or data warehouse. If the analyst has doubts about the quality and information content of the source data, then, if necessary, he can use procedures for assessing their quality, cleaning or enrichment, which are also integral parts of the data consolidation process.

The main requirement for OLTP systems is fast servicing of relatively simple requests from a large number of users, while the waiting time for a typical request to be executed should not exceed several seconds. Over time, such systems began to accumulate large volumes of data - documents, information on banking transactions, information on clients, concluded transactions, services rendered, etc.

Gradually, it became clear that data collection is not an end in itself. The collected information can be very useful in the process of managing an organization, searching for ways to improve activities and thereby gaining competitive advantages[3]. But this requires systems that would allow performing not only the simplest actions on data: calculating sums, averages, maximum and minimum values. There was a need for information systems that would allow for deep analytical processing, which requires solving such problems as searching for hidden structures and patterns in data arrays, deriving rules from them that a given subject area obeys, strategic and operational

planning, generating ad hoc requests, making decisions and predicting their consequences[4]. Understanding the advantages that intelligent analysis can provide led to the emergence of a new class of systems - information systems for decision support (information DSS), focused on analytical data processing in order to obtain knowledge necessary for developing management solutions. Additional incentives for improving these systems were such factors as the reduction in the cost of high-performance computers and expenses for storing large amounts of information, the emergence of the ability to process large amounts of data, and the development of appropriate mathematical methods. A generalized structural diagram of the information DSS is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. The process of consolidating data between information systems.

The basis of such DSS is the queries addressed to it by the user (the decision maker (DM) - manager, expert or analyst). At the same time, the queries allowed in traditional operational data processing systems are very primitive. At the same time, the analytical system can answer much more complex queries, for example: "Determine the average time between issuing and paying an invoice for each category of clients"[5].

In the process of developing information analysis systems and the methodology for their application, it was discovered that for effective functioning such systems should be organized in a slightly different way than that used in OLTP systems. To execute complex analytical queries, it is necessary to process large arrays of data from various sources. To execute queries related to trend analysis and forecasting of long-term processes, historical data accumulated over a sufficiently long period is required, which is not provided by conventional OLTP systems[7].

The data used for the purposes of analysis and servicing analytical queries differ from that used in conventional OLTP systems. During analytical processing, preference is given to generalized (aggregated) data rather than detailed data. Obviously, for analyzing sales of a large supermarket, it is not information about individual purchases that is of interest, but rather information about sales over certain time intervals (for example, a week or a month).

The process of developing a DW is very labor-intensive; some organizations spend several months and even years on it, and also invest significant financial resources[6]. The main tasks that need to be solved in the process of developing a DW are:

- selecting a data storage structure that ensures high query execution speed and minimizes the amount of RAM;
- initial filling and subsequent replenishment of the storage;
- ensuring a unified methodology for working with heterogeneous data and creating a user-friendly interface.

The range of data mining tasks is very wide, and the tasks themselves vary significantly in complexity. Therefore, depending on the specifics of the tasks being solved and their complexity, the architecture of the data warehouse and the data models used to build them may differ. A generalized conceptual diagram of the data warehouse is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Conceptual structure of data storage on distributed servers.

According to the scheme, data is extracted from various sources and loaded into a data warehouse, which contains both the actual data, presented in accordance with a certain model, and metadata (Fig.4)

Fig. 4. A method of consolidating information flow on distributed servers.

All methods of the algorithm under consideration, taking into account the classifications of Data Mining, are divided into two large groups according to the principle of working with the initial training data:

- 1) direct use of data - manifests itself at the stage of direct work with samples from the database and making the necessary changes [8] to the sets of details of individuals;
- 2) identification and use of formalized patterns, or template distillation - used in a fuzzy search for a specific individual from multiple data sets present in the database (Fig.5).

Fig. 5. A comprehensive algorithm for searching for individuals in a database based on fuzzy comparison.

The proposed algorithm, the block diagram of which is shown in Fig. 1, includes the following stages[9].

1. Determination of a list of completely identical sets of details of individuals.

A search for individuals is carried out by direct comparison of details.

2. Preparation of data for analysis.

In the absence of details completely identical to those sought, a larger selection is made, including about 300-500 sets remotely similar to those sought. An example of such a request:

```
CURSOR persons IS
SELECT p.person_id, p.lastname, p.firstname, p.patronymic, p.birthdate FROM work.person p
WHERE (((SOUNDEX(TO_TRANSLIT(p.lastname)) = SOUNDEX(TO_TRANSLIT(fo_
Lastname))))
AND (SOUNDEX(TO_TRANSLIT(p.firstname)) = SOUNDEX(TO_TRANSLIT(fo_Firstname))))
OR ((SOUNDEX(TO_TRANSLIT(p.lastname)) = SOUNDEX(TO_TRANSLIT(fo_Lastname))))
```



```
AND(SOUNDEX(TO_TRANSLIT(p.patronymic))=SOUNDEX(TO_TRANSLIT(fo_Patronymic))))
OR ((SOUNDEX(TO_TRANSLIT(p.firstname)) = SOUNDEX(TO_TRANSLIT(fo_Firstname)))
AND (SOUNDEX(TO_TRANSLIT(p.patronymic)) = SOUNDEX(TO_TRANSLIT(fo_Patronymic))));
```

3. Variant comparison of similar attributes.

Sequential enumeration of an array of similar sets and assignment of patterns to them. At this stage, new patterns are also identified.

Data sets are determined in accordance with the selected models. Unfound initial sets of details are output to the report for manual processing by the operator.

Based on the results of manual processing, the stored models are adjusted to improve the quality of the search in subsequent identification sessions[11]. In the developed implementation of the algorithm in the PL – SQL language of the Oracle 18g DBMS, the key functions are assigned to the logically allocated procedures *COMPARISON_STRING* and *COMPARISON_NUMBER*, which allow for intelligent comparison of two similar strings or numbers, taking into account possible inaccuracies or input errors. These procedures can be used not only to identify details, but also wherever full-text search with fuzzy input data is required.

Technical and economic indicators of the algorithm For a comparative analysis of the developed algorithm, we will consider the identification technology based on direct comparison. When using this technology, the emphasis is on the speed of record processing, rather than on the quality of the system’s decision-making. As a result, after the completion of the procedure based on direct comparison, there remains a lot of data (about 20-30% of the total number of lines) that are not related to the original data, which must be processed manually, which is extremely difficult with large volumes of processed data. As a test environment, consolidated city population databases with the number of records 800 0000, Oracle 11g DBMS, HP ProLiant DL160 G6 server were selected[12]. The performance indicators of the two algorithms are shown in the table. From this, we can conclude that the developed algorithm minimizes the operator’s work on manual processing of results, i.e. although the processing speed is somewhat lower, the algorithm allows to significantly unload the operators due to the intelligent decision-making system, which the direct comparison algorithm cannot offer (table 1).

Table 1. Indicators of an efficient algorithm.

Indicators	Algorithm	
	direct comparition	fuzzy comparition
Data processing speed, lines/hour	~ 100 000	~ 80 000
Identification accuracy (probability of accurate search of details), %	~ 80	~ 99,8

When comparing the economic characteristics of the developed software based on the described algorithm with the direct comparison procedure for the annual identification volume of 1,200,000 individuals, the following data were obtained(Fig. 5): labor costs for processing information using the fuzzy comparison method compared to the direct comparison method were reduced by 6.7 times, the absolute reduction in labor costs was 1446 hours, annual costs when using the fuzzy comparison method were reduced by 3 times compared to the same period of using the direct comparison method, and the annual economic effect exceeded 580,000 0000 (million) sums.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Self-learning systems allow you to free up human resources to perform creative tasks. In this area, Data Mining technology provides a full set of theoretical and practical tools for selecting, developing or using intelligent computer systems.

The identification procedure considered in the article can be regarded as part of a decision support system. The procedure does not require operator intervention, accumulates experience and self-learns in the process of work, thereby allowing to completely free specialists from inefficient manual work directly with sets of details of individuals stored in the database. This procedure is implemented in the PL-SQL language of the Oracle 18g DBMS and has been successfully functioning since November 2024 in the municipal institution “Tashkent Information Center (Tax Administration)”. The logical structure of the developed algorithm allows it to be implemented in any popular programming language. In the future, this algorithm can be implemented in the systems of the global unification of repositories of state or commercial organizations to maintain a single database of the population of any country in the world. The scalability of the algorithm allows the use of software procedures based on it both in small organizations and in large corporations, i.e. wherever the register of individuals’ data is maintained and updated. Possible examples of use: a government services portal, medical electronic systems, personnel and accounting systems for employee records, tax system, banking systems for storing customer data, etc.

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